

Mysteries of Sex in the House of the Hidden Light: Arthur Edward Waite and the Kabbalah

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The British poet, amateur historian, and prodigious author Arthur Edward Waite (1857-1942)¹ is not easy to categorize. He has often been perceived as a typical representative of Victorian occultism, and for good reasons, given his life-long involvement in organizations such as the Hermetic Order of the Golden Dawn or his self-created Fellowship of the Rosy Cross. From his own mature perspective, however, the magical pursuits of occultist organizations should be rejected in favor of an idiosyncratic form of Christian *mysticism*; and in this regard, Waite's development is reminiscent of that of one of his chief heroes, Louis-Claude de Saint-Martin (1743-1803) (the 'unknown philosopher'), who, in a similar manner, had distanced himself from the practical theurgy of Martinez de Pasqually's (1709 or 1726/27-1774) Elus Coens and its successor movements, in favor of a pious inner-directed Christianity inspired by the Christian theosophy of Jacob Böhme (1575-1624).² The precise nature of Waite's intimate beliefs is not easy to discern, to say the least. His strange, difficult, and ponderous style of writing, his infuriatingly vague way of referring to what he saw as the mysterious reality at work in religious history, his continuous revisions of earlier writings, the fact that he never attempted a synthetic overview of 'the secret tradition' he believed to be at work in history, and his refusal to disclose his inner thoughts in writing or even to those who were close to him – all these factors conspire to keep his actual perspective frustratingly elusive. Even his intimate friend Arthur Machen (1863-1947) was at a loss: 'I have known my very dear friend A. E. Waite for 38 years; and I have not

¹ For Waite's life see R.A. Gilbert, *A.E. Waite: Magician of Many Parts*, Wellingborough 1987.

² See Waite's own biography of Saint-Martin (A.E. Waite, *The Unknown Philosopher: The Life of Louis Claude de Saint-Martin and the Substance of His Transcendental Doctrine* [orig. 1901], Blauvelt 1970) and the modern study by Nicole Jacques-Lefèvre, *Louis-Claude de Saint-Martin, le philosophe inconnu (1743-1803)*, Paris 2003.

the faintest notion as to his real beliefs'.³ Perhaps the clearest statement appears in Waite's autobiography *Shadows of Life and Thought* (1938), where he discusses his initiatic drama 'The Book of the King's Dole', published in his *Strange Houses of Sleep* (1906):

I believe to this day that ['The Book of the King's Dole'] is a pregnant illustration of truth in the spiritual world; that there is a Church behind the Church on a more inward plane of being; and that it is formed of those who have opened the iridescent shell of external doctrine and have found that which abides within it. It is a Church of more worlds than one, for some of the Community are among us here and now and some are in a stage beyond the threshold of the physical senses. Eckartshausen spoke of it as he could in clouded terms. Loupuhim [sic] was far too much under the influence of the outward forms to be called a chief witness; but at least he bore his testimony, from however far away. There may be well enough such a Holy Assembly at the back of some other great religions. If so, they constitute a Blessed Company in a realm of the Blessed Life. It does not follow that they are in direct communication with the Centre, but they are in the luminous shadow thereof.⁴

This mysterious community was believed to consist of 'men of desire' (*hommes de désir*, a terminology adopted from Saint-Martin) whose aspiration was to reverse the effects of the Fall from divine union by means of a mystical process of interior regeneration.⁵ Waite referred to those who had managed to achieve that goal (whether in this life or in the next) as the 'Holy Assembly', and suspected or believed that the members of this invisible community of mystical initiates had somehow been at work discreetly, in a hidden 'inward' manner, since ancient times, through historical traditions such as alchemy and Kabbalah.

³ Arthur Machen to Colin Summerford in 1925, as quoted in Gilbert, *A.E. Waite: Magician*, p. 163.

⁴ A.E. Waite, *Shadows of Life and Thought: A Retrospective Review in the Form of Memoirs*, London 1938, pp. 170-171. References are to Ivan Vladimirovich Lopukhin, *Quelques traits de l'Église Intérieure, de l'unique chemin, qui mène à la vérité, et des diverses routes, qui conduisent à l'erreur et à la perte*, St. Petersburg 1798; and to various works by Karl von Eckartshausen (1752-1803); see the section on the notion of the 'interior church' in Antoine Faivre, *Eckartshausen et la théosophie chrétienne*, Paris 1969, pp. 374-386.

⁵ On the history of this notion, see Mike A. Zuber, 'Spiritual Alchemy from the Age of Jacob Boehme to Mary Atwood', Ph.D. dissertation: University of Amsterdam 2017.

Waite as a Scholar of Kabbalah

If Waite's position between occultist magic and Christian mysticism is quite ambiguous, one can say the same about his position halfway between the perspective of a practitioner and that of a scholar and historian. Without the benefit of any proper academic training, he made his name as an extremely productive amateur historian, publishing a long series of voluminous and erudite books on Rosicrucianism, the Occult Sciences, Magic, Kabbalah, Mysticism, the Graal tradition, Freemasonry, and the Tarot.⁶ Since these domains had been seriously neglected by the academy throughout the nineteenth century, Waite had very little competition, and his oeuvre came to dominate the English-language book market for historical scholarship in what we nowadays refer to as Western esotericism.⁷ The negative effects have been considerable, as pointed out by Lawrence M. Principe and William R. Newman for the domain of alchemy:

[Waite's editions] are almost invariably based upon corrupt editions and offer texts butchered to unrecognizability by the silent excision of large portions of material and adulterated by the addition of occultist elements and slants completely alien to the originals. [...] Waite's corrupt translations were used regularly by historians of science until the middle of this century, as witnessed by their frequent citation in articles in *Ambix* and *Isis*, as well as in scholarly books; some authors still continue to refer to them. Nearly all have been reprinted and are currently available in inexpensive editions.⁸

Among the various fields covered by Waite's researches, it is only in the domain of Kabbalah that scholarly standards began to improve at a relatively early date, due to the work of Gershom Scholem. In *Major Trends of Jewish Mysticism*, he provided a remarkably balanced and fair assessment, pointing out that if well-meaning but insufficiently qualified amateurs such as Waite could have such an impact on the study of Kabbalah, this meant that better qualified scholars had not been doing their job:

⁶ Complete overview in R.A. Gilbert, *A.E. Waite: A Bibliography*, Wellingborough 1983.

⁷ Wouter J. Hanegraaff, *Esotericism and the Academy: Rejected Knowledge in Western Culture*, Cambridge 2012, pp. 247-252.

⁸ Lawrence Principe and William R. Newman, 'Some Problems with the Historiography of Alchemy', *Secrets of Nature: Astrology and Alchemy in Early Modern Europe* ed. W. R. Newman and A. Grafton, Cambridge, Mass. 2001, pp. 1-37, 385-431, here p. 395.

It is not to the credit of Jewish scholarship that the works of the few writers who were really informed on the subject were never printed, and in some cases were not even recorded, since there was nobody to take an interest. Nor have we reason to be proud of the fact that the greater part of the ideas and views which show a real insight into the world of Kabbalism, closed as it was to the rationalism prevailing in the Judaism of the nineteenth century, were expressed by Christian scholars of a mystical bent, such as the Englishman Arthur Edward Waite in our days [...] It is a pity that the fine philosophical intuition and natural grasp of such students lost their edge because they lacked all critical sense as to historical and philological data in this field, and therefore failed completely when they had to handle problems bearing on the facts. [I]t is all the more regrettable that [Waite's *Secret Doctrine in Israel*] is marred by an uncritical attitude towards facts of history and philology.⁹

In an earlier review of Waite's *Holy Kabbalah*, published in 1931, Scholem had been even more explicit. He described Waite not only as 'one of England's most outstanding mystical writers', but as one who 'at the same time [...] has an understanding – so rare among authors who are standing on the ground of mysticism – for the importance of historical criticism'. Nevertheless, Waite's sincere attempts at doing serious historical research had been to no avail:

[A]lthough [Waite's *Holy Kabbalah*] unquestionably towers high above everything else that has been written about kabbalah from theosophical and mystical perspectives, in this book we are dealing, nevertheless, with one of the most disturbing documents of the catastrophic conflict between mystical and critical intuition. Admittedly, as he often stresses himself, the author is writing for readers of the first kind (and for these, his merits in the direction of criticism remain considerable), but the entire nature of the book will undoubtedly cause it to be disseminated more broadly and to be brought to the attention of scholarly-oriented readers as well.¹⁰

And that, of course, is the problem. Scholem expressed respect for Waite's 'amazing diligence' in seeking to discern the meaning of Kabbalistic literature from the sources that were available to him, but had to conclude that all these efforts were wasted because Waite lacked the elementary technical expertise needed for the job. Amazing as it may be for an author who published such large tomes on a Jewish tradition, the sobering fact is

⁹ Gershom G. Scholem, *Major Trends in Jewish Mysticism*, New York 1974, p. 2 (and see also his further statements on p. 212).

¹⁰ Gershom G. Scholem, 'Review of A.E. Waite, *The Holy Kabbalah*', *Orientalistische Literaturzeitung* 7 (1931), pp. 633-638, here pp. 633-634.

that Waite did not know Hebrew or Aramaic and relied entirely on translations: his original source was Christian Knorr von Rosenroth's (1636-1689) *Kabbala Denudata*, eventually supplemented by Jean de Pauly's (1860-1903) French *Zohar* translation, which caused him to adopt that author's frequent Christian misinterpretations along with his outright forgeries.¹¹ No less fatally, Scholem continued, Waite appeared to be ignorant of almost all the modern literature on Kabbalah, so that what he wrote about its origins, development, and decline was 'for 80% wholly without foundation'.¹² Finally, although Waite claimed to have searched hard for manuscripts, he was blissfully unaware of the relevant holdings even in the British Museum, not to mention manuscripts in Oxford, Munich, and so on. Scholem's conclusions were therefore unavoidable: 'it is only with sincere regret about the fatal disproportion between [Waite's] great labors and the depth of understanding that was possible for him, on the one hand, and [his] so sadly deficient knowledge of original sources and a useful historical-critical foundation, on the other hand, that one will have to put this book aside'.¹³ In sum: even though Waite's sense of historical criticism may have been superior to that of other contemporary esoteric writers on Kabbalah, it still remained extremely inadequate. He simply lacked the proper instruments needed for the task of really understanding Jewish Kabbalah. Nevertheless, in spite of these failings, by relying on sheer intuition he occasionally got it right. Significantly, as will be seen, Scholem found this to be especially true in regard to (in Waite's formulation) 'the mystery of sex'. In Scholem's words, 'Valuable in this book is the unprejudiced and penetrating attempt to understand the sexual symbolism of the Kabbalah, in which Waite, with good intuition, has perceived one of the kabbala's central positions'.¹⁴ To this we will return.

As regards Waite's essential contribution to Kabbalah scholarship, I do not think there is much to add to Scholem's verdict. However, it may be interesting to take a closer look at his position halfway between nineteenth-century occultist views of Kabbalah, on the one hand, and modern scholarly views, on the other. In this regard, one had hoped to profit from Liz Greene's

¹¹ Waite defended his reliance on De Pauly against Robert Eisler (1882-1949) and Gershom Scholem in A.E. Waite, *The Holy Kabbalah*, London 1929, p. 8 nt 1.

¹² Scholem, 'Review', p. 635.

¹³ *Ibid.*, p. 638.

¹⁴ *Ibid.*, p. 638.

voluminous recent monograph about the Kabbalah in British occultism,¹⁵ but unfortunately it does not help us much further. Greene herself appears to adhere to a perennialist view of ‘the’ Kabbalah that dismisses differences between medieval Jewish Kabbalah, early modern Christian Kabbalah, or Victorian occultist Kabbalah as mere surface appearances that cause us to lose sight of their universal essence.¹⁶ Instead, she sets out to vindicate or rehabilitate the occultist Kabbalah as an authentic manifestation of ‘the real Kabbalah’, against the perceived threat of modern criticism and its emphasis on historical specificity.¹⁷ The essential message of modern textual criticism still does not seem to have sunk in, for Greene follows Waite’s example in assuming that one can speak with authority about the ‘real’ nature of Jewish Kabbalah even if one cannot read the relevant languages: ‘I make no claim to any expertise in reading medieval Hebrew manuscripts; Kabbalistic texts are cited in their English translations’.¹⁸ It remains a mystery to me how, on this basis, one can make such firm statements as she does about the essential

¹⁵ Liz Greene, *Magi and Maggidim: The Kabbalah in British Occultism 1860-1940*, Ceredigion 2012, pp. 301-332.

¹⁶ Regarding Christian Kabbalah, Greene claims that its ‘fundamentals’ do not differ from those of Jewish Kabbalah: ‘What is Christian about the ‘Christian’ Kabbalah is the intent of its adherents, rather than the Kabbalah itself’ (ibid., pp. 10-11). How and where the evidence for this ‘Kabbalah itself’ is to be found, and how it should be distinguished from the historically specific perspectives or ‘intent’ of those who write about it is not explained. Misrepresenting my argument about nineteenth-century concepts – common among both scholars and occultists before Scholem – of a ‘universal Kabbalah’ with non-Jewish roots, Greene seems to assume that it implies a denial on my part of contact and exchange between Jews and their neighbours in earlier periods, or of Greek and Hellenistic influences on Kabbalistic and Hasidic writings (ibid, p. 8). For the actual argument, which makes no such claims, see Wouter J. Hanegraaff, ‘The Beginnings of Occultist Kabbalah: Adolphe Franck and Eliphaz Lévi’, *Kabbalah and Modernity: Interpretations, Transformations, Adaptations*, ed. B. Huss, M. Pasi and K. von Stuckrad, Leiden / Boston 2010, pp. 107-128.

¹⁷ Given these essentialist assumptions, it is no surprise that she rejects the idea of an ‘empirical’ methodology grounded in textual criticism (Greene, *Magi and Maggidim*, pp. 23-32). More puzzling is why she finds it necessary to accuse its representatives, without providing any arguments, of ‘methodolatry’ and exclusivist or doctrinal leanings (‘espousing an academic paradigm as though it were a biblical truth’, ibid., 25). Unfortunately, Greene’s section ‘Methodologies, Methodolatries, and Metanarratives’ is riddled with so many inaccuracies and misunderstandings of the approaches she dislikes that it seems pointless to refute them.

¹⁸ Ibid., p. 37.

unity of ‘the’ Kabbalah from Jewish medieval sources to those of modern Christian occultists.

Even though Waite’s Kabbalah scholarship fell short of the standards of modern historical criticism, it was still a considerable step forward compared to the original occultist position. The Kabbalah assumed a central place in nineteenth-century occultism thanks to the works of its virtual founder, Alphonse-Louis Constant, better known as Eliphas Lévi (1810-1875). In an article published in 2010,¹⁹ I analyzed this author in connection with his main counterpart on the academic side, Adolphe Franck (1810-1893). I showed that Franck and Lévi both thought of the Kabbalah as a universal tradition with non-Jewish ‘Zoroastrian’ origins and I argued that Lévi’s perspective was grounded essentially in the *prisca theologia* tradition of the Renaissance, derived from Patristic foundations that were well known to him from his Roman Catholic upbringing and his education for the priesthood.²⁰ Lévi’s understanding of Kabbalah was a high Romantic literary invention of considerable brilliance and originality, although obviously lacking in any historical foundation. Waite, for his part, noted in his *Doctrine and Literature of the Kabalah* (1902) – to which we will return – that ‘few have approached the subject with sympathies in the direction of occult science and philosophy who do not owe their introduction to Eliphas Lévi’,²¹ but then proceeded to criticize him at length. Just a few years earlier, Waite had still believed that Lévi ‘had received initiation into a school of traditional knowledge’,²² but in the meantime he had clearly become disillusioned: ‘I do not think that he [Lévi] ever made an independent statement upon any historical fact to which the least confidence could be given with prudence’.²³ The only point on which he still agreed with his French predecessor was precisely Lévi’s non-historical perennialism (‘that there is a religion behind all religions’); but he had come to dismiss Lévi’s assumption that this religion ‘is the veiled mystery of Kabalism, from which all have issued and into which all return’.²⁴ Instead, he now held that the

¹⁹ Hanegraaff, ‘Beginnings’.

²⁰ For this point, cf. Hanegraaff, *Esotericism and the Academy*, pp. 244-247. In terms of my analysis in *ibid.*, pp. 12-17 and pp. 28ff (esp. pp. 53-68), Lévi’s perspective on Kabbalah can be seen as a latter-day permutation of the ‘Zoroastrian’ variant of Platonic Orientalism (rather than the ‘Mosaic’ variant typical of Pico della Mirandola’s original conception of Christian Kabbalah).

²¹ A.E. Waite, *The Doctrine and Literature of the Kabalah*, London 1902, p. 398.

²² *Ibid.*, p. 399.

²³ *Ibid.*, pp. 399-400.

²⁴ *Ibid.*, p. 407.

Jewish Kabbalah was merely one of multiple channels through which the original ‘secret doctrine’ could be accessed.

Waite’s Three Books on Kabbalah

It would seem that Waite began his Kabbalistic studies out of a sincere belief in the occultist doctrine of a universal Kabbalah as proclaimed by Eliphas Lévi. Eventually, however, he came to dismiss it as incompatible with what he learned from the sources at his disposal. Scholem is quite right in pointing out that, in spite of his evident deficiencies, he still had a much better sense of historical criticism than was usual among occultists or mystics of his generation, and it is on this basis that he began to draw conclusions of his own and create a new synthesis as best as he could. The first product of his researches was ready by 1899, but publication was delayed due to a disastrous fire at the building of the Press, which destroyed the sheets and type. It was finally published in 1902, not by the original publisher Redway but by the Theosophical Publishing Society in London, under the title *The Doctrine and Literature of the Kabalah*. Waite’s second large book on Kabbalah was published eleven years later, in 1913, as *The Secret Doctrine in Israel: A Study of the Zohar and its Connections*. His third and final volume on the subject, *The Holy Kabbalah* was published in 1929; however, this was not an entirely new book but a thoroughly reworked, revised, and updated combination of materials taken from the 1902 and 1913 volumes.

In all three books, Waite presented the Kabbalah as consisting essentially of *Sefer Yeşirah* and the *Zohar*. He had a very restrictive view of what Kabbalah was all about: for instance, he dismissed magical elements as extraneous to its real nature (e.g. ‘it is by the perversion of the Kabalah that we have obtained the grimoires’²⁵) and ridiculed exegetical techniques such as *gematria* as silly aberrations (‘these solemn follies, which appear so childish and ridiculous at the present day’²⁶). About non-*Zoharic* Kabbalists such as Abraham Abulafia (‘a quixotic adventurer and a Messianic enthusiast, whose opinions it is unnecessary to determine’²⁷) or Isaac Luria (‘a wild fantasist’ whose doctrine ‘is greatly curious, yet fitly described as a reverie’²⁸) he had not much positive to say.

Chapters one to six and nine to eleven of *The Holy Kabbalah* were largely reworked versions of *The Doctrine and Literature of the Kabalah*.

²⁵ Waite, *Doctrine and Literature*, p. 445 (and see the whole of his chapter ‘The Kabalah and Magic’, *ibid.*, pp. 438-449).

²⁶ Waite, *Holy Kabbalah*, p. 36.

²⁷ *Ibid.*, pp. 92-93.

²⁸ *Ibid.*, pp. 413, 420.

Regarding the contents of these chapters, basically, Waite did not change his mind between 1899 and 1929. Chapters seven and eight, however, were new. Here one sees the influence of Waite's analysis of the *Zohar* that had been published as chapters five to seventeen of *The Secret Doctrine in Israel*. The main factor that accounts for the development of Waite's ideas between 1899 and 1929 was Waite's thorough study of Jean de Pauly's French *Zohar* translation, published in six volumes from 1906-1911.²⁹ This work convinced him of the centrality to *Zoharic* mysticism of what he came to refer to as 'the mystery of sex'. Chapter seven of *The Holy Kabbalah* (based upon chapters five to fifteen of *The Secret Doctrine in Israel*) was titled 'Ways of God with Man', and discussed the myth of the earthly paradise, the serpent of Genesis, the Fall of the angels and the Fall of Man, the legend of the deluge, the covenant with Abraham, Moses and the Law, the Temple in Jerusalem, the expectation of the Messiah, the doctrine of *Sheol*, and ideas about resurrection. Chapters sixteen and seventeen of his *Zohar* analysis of 1913 were set apart and turned into a separate chapter in *The Holy Kabbalah*. This chapter eight was titled 'The Higher Secret Doctrine', and it was here that Waite discussed what he saw as the true heart of *Zoharic* and hence of Kabbalistic mysticism. These two chapters discussed 'the mystery of Shekinah' and 'the mystery of sex', and we have seen that even Scholem spoke of them with a remarkable degree of respect. Interestingly, we will see that precisely in these discussions of Kabbalistic eroticism, Waite came closest to expressing his personal understanding of 'true mysticism'. That understanding, however, was ultimately grounded not in Waite's study of Jewish Kabbalah but in intimate personal experiences that had very little to do with Jewish tradition. In all likelihood, or so I would suggest, it is only *because* of those experiences that De Pauly's discussion of Kabbalistic sex practices had such an impact and made so much sense to Waite. In her dissertation discussed above, Liz Greene rightly points towards a connection between 'the mystery of sex' and a remarkable book published in 1904 by Waite together with his friend Arthur Machen and titled *The House of the Hidden Light*.³⁰ Although my interpretation differs from hers, I agree that this title is crucial to Waite's oeuvre as a whole. So what is this book all about, and what is its relevance to Waite's Kabbalah?

²⁹ Jean de Pauly, *Sepher ha-Zohar (Le livre de la splendeur)*, 6 vols., Paris 1906-1911.

³⁰ Greene, *Magi and Maggidim*, pp. 326-327.

The Transformation of Desire

The House of the Hidden Light is an extreme rarity. Published in 1904 by ‘The High Fratres Filius Aquarum and Elias Artista’, its print-run was limited to exactly three copies, two for the authors and one for the publisher. It is therefore fortunate that the leading Waite specialist R. A. Gilbert published a new edition (limited to 350 hand-signed copies) in 2003. The book consists of thirty-five letters that were exchanged between Waite (‘Frater Elias Artista’) and Arthur Machen (‘Frater Filius Aquarum’), preceded by an Introduction titled ‘The Pastoral’ and two Tables of Contents. As seen from the opening sentences of ‘The Pastoral’, *The House of the Hidden Light* presents itself as a book of deep secrets and mysteries:

It is known, beloved, among those who have partaken of the mysteries, who have eaten the bread of angels and have communicated in the cup of memory, that Nature is a secret doctrine variously expounded in accordance with the hierarchic distributions of the True Word, with the symbols and the substitutes thereof. But the magisterial interpretation is classed among the King’s secrets, whereof it has been said – *Abscondere bonum est*. It is not to be supposed that such a secret is attained except hardly or that it is disclosed lightly, but there are orders of initiation and degrees of reception by which the proselytes are led upwards, and are guided in the recovery of those treasures of which they are the heirs, natural and elected.³¹

This sample of mystery language is typical for the book as a whole. So what are those mysteries, secrets, and treasures? What is this book all about? The thirty-five letters exchanged between Waite and Machen refer to what the two friends saw as their *annus mirabilis*, which had begun in the autumn of 1899. The artist and occultist Ithell Colquhoun has suggested in 1975 that they had been experimenting with ‘sexual congress with praeternatural beings’,³² but Robert Gilbert has shown convincingly that this is a myth.³³ While the book does have a real ‘hidden’ meaning, it refers to practices that – at first sight at least – would seem to be remarkably non-esoteric. Waite and Machen had quite simply been enjoying a series of late-night evenings of heavy drinking (alcohol, absinth) and wide-ranging discussions in

³¹ Anonymus, *The House of the Hidden Light, Manifested and Set Forth in Certain Letters Communicated from a Lodge of the Adepts by The High Fratres Filius Aquarum and Elias Artista* [orig. 1904], Carlton-in-Coverdale 2003, pp. 1-2.

³² Ithell Colquhoun, *Sword of Wisdom: MacGregor Mathers and ‘The Golden Dawn’*, London 1975, p. 288.

³³ R.A. Gilbert, ‘Introduction’, Anonymus, *House of the Hidden Light*, pp. v-vi.

London taverns, together with two intimate female friends and some other companions. Through the exalted esoteric language of *The House of the Hidden Light*, these meetings are transformed into initiatic events of deep spiritual importance. As Gilbert puts it, they were ‘a mixture of high intent and low practice’.³⁴

To explain what was going on, some biographical background is necessary. Arthur Machen’s dearly beloved wife Amy Hogg had died of cancer earlier in 1899, after a sickbed of six years, and this loss had a devastating effect on him. In his autobiographical notes *Things Near and Far*, he describes how, sitting at home one afternoon in November, ‘a horror of soul that cannot be uttered descended upon me’; and in his acute despair, he decided to experiment with a certain ‘process’ to dull the pain.³⁵ Unfortunately we do not know what that process involved, but whatever it was, it appears to have had an incredible effect on him.

What I received was not a mere dull lack of painful sensation, but a peace of the spirit that was quite ineffable, a knowledge that all hurts and doles and wounds were healed [...] Everything, of body and of mind, was resolved into an infinite and an exquisite delight; into a joy so great that – let this be duly noted – it became almost intolerable in its ecstasy.³⁶

Apparently such altered states and experiences of rapturous bliss kept returning over the next weeks or even months, and Machen describes them in terms that are reminiscent of the mystery language of *The House of the Hidden Light*. For instance, he speaks of ‘the great gusts of incense that were blown in those days into my nostrils, of the odours of rare gums that seemed to fume before invisible altars in Holborn, in Claremont Square, in grey streets of Clerkenwell, of the savours of the sanctuary that were perceived by me in all manner of grim London wastes and wanderings’.³⁷

This does not mean that the pain about Amy’s death was over, and it would seem that the drinking evenings with Waite were deeply therapeutic for Machen. He came to those evenings accompanied by a new lady friend, Vivienne Pierpoint. He sometimes called her ‘the Shepherdess’, but in *The House of the Hidden Light* she is called ‘Soror Ignis Ardens’ (Sister of the Ardent Fire) or ‘Lilith’. Waite, for his part, came accompanied by Annie Lakeman, usually referred to as Dora. Now Dora had been the love of his

³⁴ Ibid., p. xxii.

³⁵ Arthur Machen, ‘Things Near and Far’, *The Autobiography of Arthur Machen*, London 1951, p. 270.

³⁶ Ibid., pp. 272-273.

³⁷ Ibid., p. 267.

life since the first time they met, in 1886. The attraction seems to have been mutual, but Waite could not offer her financial security, and so Dora got married to a well-to-do older gentleman, Charles Granville Stuart-Menteth (1769-1847). Waite had to make do with her rather dull sister Ada, whom he married one year later. In *The House of the Hidden Light*, Dora appears under the pseudonym ‘Soror Benedicta in Aqua’ (Sister Blessed in the Water). The precise nature of the relation between Waite and Dora remains elusive, but may have developed into some kind of a clandestine erotic relationship or at least came very close. Be that as it may, the intimate evenings that these four people shared together appear to have been extremely intense, emotional, even bordering on the ecstatic.

Why did Machen and Waite, in their letters, choose to imagine these meetings as esoteric initiations, and how serious were they in doing so? As the text of the *House of the Hidden Light* progresses, one sees an increasing focus on the mystical and transcendent union of male and female; and Gilbert describes the true theme of *The House of the Hidden Light* as ‘the transformation of desire’.³⁸ To understand what that might mean, we need to take a somewhat closer look at the text. It is a literary product of considerable complexity and subtlety, and to arrive at a truly convincing exegesis one would need an extensive critical apparatus of footnotes identifying the multiple allusions to biblical, Kabbalistic, alchemical, Arthurian, and other materials, as well as to the writings of Machen and Waite – not to mention the many heavily concealed references to real events in the life of the protagonists. What follows is just a very short and preliminary overview.

In ‘The Pastoral’ that precedes the letters, Machen and Waite appear as ‘two poor brothers of the spirit, friends of God and members of the sodality, having dwelt after the common manner of men in the desert of this mortal life’.³⁹ In ‘taverns by the way’, during the *annus mirabilis*, they receive ‘a certain consecration and infusion of light and a participation in the glory’.⁴⁰ Eventually, they are solemnly admitted into the hall of the Neophytes.

At this time also there were given unto them two sisters, daughters of the House of Life, for high priestesses and ministers. Into the hands of these sisters were put wands of enchantment, wands of sorcery, wands of power, with liturgies and rituals written in sibyltine books, from which they sang and celebrated throughout the wonderful year. These were children of the

³⁸ Gilbert, ‘Introduction’, p. xxvi.

³⁹ Anonymus, *House of the Hidden Light*, p. 3.

⁴⁰ *Ibid.*, p. 4.

elements, queens of fire and water, full of inward magic and of outward witchery, full of music and of song, radiant with the illusions of Light.⁴¹

The two poor brothers then proceed ‘through many sub-grades of the Secret Order of the Dawn’.⁴² The *annus mirabilis* now comes to an end, and with it the First Degree of initiation. The two brothers enter a period of spiritual darkness and deprivation, waiting anxiously for signs that announce the mysteries of the Second Degree. Finally, ‘they heard bells ringing and a great voice crying: *Introibo ad Altare Dei*’,⁴³ and they are admitted to a new sanctuary. Presumably this refers to Machen’s ‘Order of Tossspots’ created in 1901 – another drinking group, but characteristically described in *The House of the Hidden Light* as an order concerned with ‘mysteries of the Second Degree, mysteries of the Golden Order, mysteries of compassion and of unction, mysteries of healing, mysteries of the purgation of joy’.⁴⁴ The mysteries of the Third and highest Degree have not yet been attained, but of these ‘in due time there may be put forth a true memorial’.⁴⁵

‘The Pastoral’ is followed by two Tables of Contents, in which the thirty-five letters exchanged between the brothers are described in two quite different ways: first as ‘Aphorisms and Maxims of the Secret Mystery According to the Order of the Light’, and then as ‘Versicles and Symbols of the Secret Order According to the Mysteries of Love’.⁴⁶ The symbolism of Light is indeed pervasive throughout the book, as indicated by its very title: its permutations are fascinating and would deserve an extensive analysis. The symbolism of Love is frequently alluded to as well, but in a somewhat more indirect manner.

In the First letter (written ‘From a Tarrying place of the Fraternity’), Elias Artista (Waite) is invited by Filius Aquarum (Machen) to participate in ‘the Veritable, Ancient and Rectified Rite of לילית [Lilith]’⁴⁷ (a reference, as we have seen, to Machen’s female partner Vivienne Pierpoint). The invitation is written, of course, in exalted mystery language full of biblical references, allusions to the Arthurian Legends, alchemical symbolism, and so on. Elias Artista responds positively in the next letter (‘From the Passes of the East’), and presumably the series of late-night evenings now begins. Around the time of the tenth letter (‘From Within the Circles of Light’),

⁴¹ Ibid., p. 5.

⁴² Ibid., p. 5.

⁴³ Ibid., p. 7.

⁴⁴ Ibid., p. 7.

⁴⁵ Ibid., p. 8.

⁴⁶ Ibid., pp. 11-21.

⁴⁷ Ibid., p. 23.

however, something seems to have happened: the next letters indicate that Soror Ignis Ardens (Lilith) has left, and this departure of Vivienne Pierpoint is interpreted by the two brothers as an event of deep initiatic significance. With Dora Stuart-Menteath there seem to be problems too: for instance, in letter fourteen ('In the Place of Admonishment'), Machen reports that he has received 'tidings recently from our venerable and elect sister *Benedicta in Aqua*, which to my judgment shows that a certain purging is being operated within her, and that her soul longs for the Light. But she alleges that you have altogether neglected her. How is this, brother in the Light'?⁴⁸

The next letters are replete with dense gnostic, alchemical, and platonic symbolism referring to processes of purgation, liberation, purification, and sublimation. It is clear from these letters that the 'transformation of desire' involves a painful and deeply emotional process of accepting the limitations of earthly love in exchange for a higher ideal of spiritual attainment. A good example is letter twenty-two ('In the Place Where They Are United'), where Machen is doing his best to comfort Waite in his sorrow over his impossible love for Dora:

And so it seems to me, *carissime doctor viae*, that these mortal things which we enjoy, and these mortal ministrants which surround us are but as promises and notes of that which shall be. For let us suppose that a man were shown a most exquisite picture of the most sweet valley in all the world, and in it the fairest abode imaginable, and with it the likeness of the most precious and desirable of all ladies: can we conceive such a man to be bitterly distressed or in any anguish, if the picture, being shown him, were taken away, with an infallible promise that presently he should enter that valley, and dwell in that prepared mansion, and be wedded for ever to that sweetest of all the maids of God? Does not a man who is athirst crave for drink rather than the choicest picture of a fountain [...] ? And so I think that our Lilith and our Lady of the Waters are but 'pictures' and 'Promises' of certain supernal and ineffable things which shall assuredly be ours if we will but proceed on our journey.⁴⁹

In his response (letter twenty-three, 'With The Doctors in the Temple'), Elias Artista writes that 'the understanding which I am daily receiving in the Words of the Sages'⁵⁰ makes it easier for him to accept the wise words of his brother. This is undoubtedly a reference to his intense studies of the Jewish Kabbalah at that time, to which we will return.

⁴⁸ Ibid., p. 71.

⁴⁹ Ibid., pp. 103-104.

⁵⁰ Ibid., p. 107.

In letter twenty-five ('From the Heart of a Pomegranate') Elias Artista wishes his brother 'secret joy and true union when the bells ring for your marriage'⁵¹ – a direct reference to Machen's actual marriage (on 25 June 1903) to Vivienne Pierpoint's successor, Dorothy Purefoy Hudleston. It is therefore clear that the mysteries of Lilith now belong to the past, or are transformed into the mysteries of a new Lilith, and Machen has found true happiness (letter twenty-six, 'From the House of the Admixture'): 'For now, in truth, the meanest cup is filled with a celestial drink, the ministrants of the flesh are stoled and crowned, and the swell and triumph of a great music drowns the idle rumours of the streets'.⁵² Waite, for his part, is resigning himself to the inevitable: the true union with his soul mate Soror Benedicta in Aqua will never take place during this life. He is now looking back at the previous events as a painful but necessary spiritual process understood in alchemical terms (letter twenty-nine, 'Beneath a New Star in Serpentarius'): 'In the time of darkness, we were purged by the Black State of the Mystic Stone. We have passed with joy triumphantly through the White State, and the greatest of all will follow, which is the glow and the redness signifying a more perfect transmutation'.⁵³ The true union will only take place in that third state, which stands under the sign of an apophatic mysticism reminiscent of Dionysius the Areopagite (letter thirty-three, 'From a Place of Setting Out'):

O Lux Lucis, fons, origo et abyssus [O Light of Light, Fountain, Origin, and Abyss], in thy light or thy darkness we know that there is a place of union, past all the ways of love, and that there the higher Lilith and the higher Benedicta are conjoined eternally in the repose of a great ecstasy, wherein we also shall rest at length when we have attained the end of our revolutions, having put off all human interest.⁵⁴

The thirty-fifth and final letter is called 'In Via Unitiva'. Elias Artista reminds Filius Aquarum that 'We have comforted one another with great and sounding words, far echoing through the halls of time ... and it is time now to make an end of these flying scrolls, with their prophecies [...] because another day is at hand'.⁵⁵ He closes with some impressive passages

⁵¹ Ibid., p. 117.

⁵² Ibid., p. 120.

⁵³ Ibid., p. 133.

⁵⁴ Ibid., p. 142.

⁵⁵ Ibid., p. 147.

of apophatic mysticism about the ultimate center of the light that is ‘neither Light nor Darkness’, and finally announces the coming of

another Order, a secret ritual, a great experiment, a joy and bliss to come. I announce to you the Order of Life. We shall need no longer to go in search of the *Soror Benedicta in Aqua* or of the *Soror Gloriosa in Igne*, for they will come to us and will dwell with us after a secret and most intimate manner, even as the life of the beloved is hidden in the life of the lover.⁵⁶

To do justice to *The House of the Hidden Light*, I suggest we should distinguish between three levels of interpretation. The first level, highlighted by Robert Gilbert in his indispensable commentary, is essentially reductive/historical: behind the impressive esoteric language, he suggests, we find no deep spiritual meanings at all but just a series of very mundane practices and events. The initiations are really just drinking parties; the mysteries consist of the erotic tension and interplay between two men and two women who cannot give in to their desires; and for the rest, the ecstasies are essentially induced by alcohol and absinth. On the second and much more serious level, however, it seems clear that *The House of the Hidden Light* describes a process of psychological healing and transformation, a deeply emotional therapeutic process through which the protagonists learn to come to terms with the inescapable realities of their lives and loves. This is one way of understanding Gilbert’s statement that the book is about ‘the transformation of desire’. But that formulation can be understood on a third and final level as well: according to such a reading, the ‘transformation of desire’ should be understood additionally in spiritual and metaphysical terms. To understand this level of significance, it is useful to place *The House of the Hidden Light* within the context of Waite’s work as a historian of the occult. Whether this third level was also significant for Machen remains very much an open question that I will not try to answer here.

The Esoteric Heart of Waite’s Kabbalah

We saw that in *The Doctrine and Literature of the Kabbalah* (finished in 1899, right before the beginning of the *annus mirabilis*), Waite had not yet discovered the ‘mystery of sex’ as the central doctrine of Kabbalah: that insight came only after his reading of De Pauly. But if we look at his way of describing that mystery in his books of 1913 and 1929, we realize that it must have been inspired quite as strongly by the very personal events and intimate experiences referred to in *The House of the Hidden Light*. In *The*

⁵⁶ Ibid., p. 151.

Holy Kabbalah, Waite emphasizes that Kabbalistic sex practices could only take place between husbands and wives: ‘the Sacred Name is never attached to an incomplete man, being one who is unmarried, or one who dies without issue’.⁵⁷ However, in an apparent attempt at downplaying civil marriage as a mere social contract without deeper spiritual import, he and Machen appear to have been involved in intense speculations about – and possibly even ritual enactments of – what they referred to, mysteriously, as ‘Hermetic Marriage’.⁵⁸ The two friends seem to have disagreed about its precise nature, and one would like to know more. But what seems evident is that Waite was looking at his ‘Soror Benedicta in Aqua’ as his true spiritual partner in the alchemical ‘mysteries of love’.

The central theme of *The House of the Hidden Light* can in fact be understood as a combination of Platonic, alchemical, and what I would call ‘elemental’ doctrines of Eros. In Plato’s *Phaedrus* and *Symposium*, the spiritual ascent from matter to the ideal is spurred on by the powerful force of Erotic desire, understood as the inborn desire of the soul to unite itself with the true source of ultimate beauty, goodness, and truth. In its original ancient Greek context, this process was understood in homoerotic terms; but heteroerotic interpretations had become prominent during the Renaissance, after Ficino (1433-1499),⁵⁹ leading eventually to what might be called a veritable ‘religion of beauty in woman’.⁶⁰ Everything indicates that Dora was the idealized image of such feminine beauty in Waite’s understanding of the mystical ascent.

The Platonic ideal of Eros has often lent support to attitudes of ascetic renunciation, because bodily love is considered just a surrogate that falls short of the spiritual ideal. But Waite was no ascetic, and had no taste for celibacy. In his mind, the erotic search for ultimate union with the Absolute merged with the alchemical imagery of sexual union between male and

⁵⁷ Waite, *Holy Kabbalah*, p. 378.

⁵⁸ Gilbert, ‘Introduction’, pp. xxiii-xxiv.

⁵⁹ See discussion in Wouter J. Hanegraaff, ‘Under the Mantle of Love: The Mystical Eroticisms of Marsilio Ficino and Giordano Bruno’, *Hidden Intercourse: Eros and Sexuality in the History of Western Esotericism* ed. W. J. Hanegraaff & J. J. Kripal, New York 2011, pp. 175-207. Interestingly, Ficino himself still presented ‘Socratic Love’ in homoerotic terms, and this must be understood in the context of his own infatuation with Giovanni Cavalcanti (ibid., pp. 184-194). The heterosexualization of Socratic Love took off after Ficino (Hanegraaff, ‘Under the Mantle of Love’, pp. 194-205).

⁶⁰ Jefferson Fletcher, *The Religion of Beauty in Woman, and Other Essays on Platonic Love in Poetry and Society*, New York 1911.

female, sun and moon, king and queen.⁶¹ The symbolism and imagery was understood in a spiritual sense, not as an escape from the body, but as a spiritual process of transmutation and purification of the *whole* person, ultimately leading up to a higher or even perfect divine state. Because Waite believed in a universal ‘secret tradition’, it was natural for him to see the Platonic and alchemical ideals as just two manifestations of the same thing.

Next to Platonism and alchemy, a third reference was present in Waite’s and, undoubtedly, Machen’s mind. As indicated by their pseudonyms, the two mystical ‘sisters’ in *The Book of the Hidden Light* are associated explicitly with fire and water, and this makes them reminiscent of the Paracelsian elemental beings (salamanders and nymphs, in this case). These had been popularized due to Henri Montfaucon de Villars’ (c. 1836-1673) famous novel *Comte de Gabalis* (1670),⁶² were picked up in Bulwer-Lytton’s even more famous occult novel *Zanoni* (1842), and had become a topic of fascination in the Hermetic Order of the Golden Dawn of which both Waite and Machen had been members. The *Comte de Gabalis* famously claimed that elemental beings had no immortal soul, but could be immortalized by means of ‘marriage’ with a human being. Writers, artists, and satiricists had been quick to explore the obvious sexy as well as humorous possibilities of that idea.⁶³ We seem to be dealing here with an important but underestimated theme in the emergence of modern occultism. For instance, the Theosophical Society was founded in 1875 during an evening at which George Henry Felt (1831-1895) claimed that he could make elementals visible through a ‘chemical and Kabbalistic process’ – a direct reference to Comte de Gabalis; and members of the Hermetic Order of the Golden Dawn had in fact been experimenting very seriously with

⁶¹ Such erotic and sexual imagery is pervasive in alchemical publications since the 15th and through the 17th centuries. For a concise discussion of its backgrounds, see Lawrence Principe, ‘Revealing Analogies: The Descriptive and Deceptive Roles of Sexuality and Gender in Latin Alchemy’, *Hidden Intercourse: Eros and Sexuality in the History of Western Esotericism* ed. W. J. Hanegraaff & J. J. Kripal, New York 2011, pp. 385-431.

⁶² See the excellent critical edition by Didier Kahn: Henri de Montfaucon de Villars, *Le Comte de Gabalis, ou entretiens sur les sciences secrètes*, Paris 2010.

⁶³ Didier Kahn, ‘L’alchimie sur la scène française au XVIe et XVIIe siècles’, *Chrysopoeia* 2:1 (1988), pp. 62-96; Kahn, ‘Introduction’, de Villars, *Comte de Gabalis*, pp. 117-136; cf. Hanegraaff, *Esotericism and the Academy*, pp. 222-230.

rituals for ‘marrying an elemental’.⁶⁴ Finally, and most relevant to our concerns, it was a commonplace among nineteenth-century occultists that this entire tradition of elemental marriages was somehow ‘Kabbalistic’. Le Montfaucon de Villars introduced *Le Comte the Gabalis* as ‘a Great Kabbalist from Germany’, and his very name was a reference to Paracelsus’ idiosyncratic understanding of ‘Gabalia’. In his oeuvre, it stood for the ancient ‘ars cabalastica’, a subcategory of magic that was supposed to have emerged among the pagans and had been transmitted through the Chaldaeans and the Hebrews.⁶⁵

Conclusion

We have seen that Waite’s mature understanding of Kabbalah was heavily influenced by De Pauly’s French *Zohar* translation (1906-1911), which caused him to focus on ‘the mysteries of sex’ as the heart of the Kabbalistic mystery. His personal understanding of those mysteries, however, reflected his intimate real-life experiences with ‘Soror Benedicta in Aqua’ as documented in *The House of the Hidden Light*. Together with Arthur Machen, Waite created an esoteric narrative of initiation that allowed them to speak of those deeply therapeutic events in the language of Christian Platonism (especially Pseudo-Dionysius the Areopagite), early modern alchemy, and occultist speculation about Elemental marriage. These non-Kabbalistic contexts must be taken into account to understand his emphasis on the erotic language of the *Zohar* and its descriptions of union with the Shekinah. Consider, for instance, this passage:

There is – in the true sense of this term – a spiritual union below for the Sons of the Doctrine, so that they are encompassed by two females – the wife who is on earth and the Unseen Helpmate. [The condition for this consists in] the raising of the heart and mind on the part of the Lover and Beloved, to the Most Holy Shekinah, the glory which cohabits and indwells, during the external act. The *absconditus sponsus* enters into the body of the woman and is joined with the *abscondita sponsa*.⁶⁶

In thinking of the *abscondita sponsa*, Waite must have imagined the transfigured image of Dora Stuart-Menteth, his ‘Soror Benedicta in Aqua’. He probably played with the idea that during the sexual act, it might be

⁶⁴ References in Hanegraaff, *Esotericism and the Academy*, p. 227 nt 286.

⁶⁵ Paracelsus, *Theologische Werke I: Vita Beata – Vom Seligen Leben*, ed. U. L. Gantenbein, Berlin / New York 2008, p. 311; cf. Kahn, ‘L’alchimie sur la scène française’, p. 94 with notes 79-80.

⁶⁶ Waite, *Holy Kabbalah*, pp. 375, 381.

possible for his soul to somehow unite with Dora's soul, even though their bodies could not. In any case, Waite seems to have lived the rest of his life in the hope or expectation that the 'Hidden Light' and the 'Mysteries of Love' would be fully revealed and celebrated on a superior plane after death: even though Arthur Edward Waite could not marry Annie (Dora) Lakeman, Elias Artista would one day be united with his Soror Benedicta in Aqua. At the heart of Waite's writings on Kabbalah, then, we find the deeply human tragedy of an unfulfilled love. It informed his reading of Kabbalistic texts and determined his choices about what was essential and what was not. Only very few people who were in on the secrets of his intimate life, then, would ever understand what chapters VII and VIII of *The Holy Kabbalah* were ultimately all about.